

Viscosity of KCl and NaCl in Aqueous Urea Solutions at 30 and 35°

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Viscosities of concentrated solutions of potassium chloride and sodium chloride in aqueous urea solutions of varying concentrations have been determined at 30 and 35°. Graphical techniques have been employed for obtaining different parameters of the viscosity equations. An empirical relation for B values, molar volume and concentration of urea is suggested. The water structure is found to be broken down in presence of urea.

WATER at ordinary temperature has a quasicrystalline structure¹. A dynamic equilibrium, $(H_2O)_6 \rightleftharpoons (H_2O)_4$, seems to exist between the three dimensional hydrogen bonded clusters and the denser monomers. Electrolytes which dissolve in water have been classified as structure makers or structure breakers, depending on whether the above equilibrium is shifted to left or right.

Urea and water are miscible with each other. Urea is basic in character whereas water is both an electron donor and an acceptor. Hence, their aqueous mixtures are an interesting field to explore, particularly of the ionic processes accompanying the solutions of strong electrolytes. It becomes relevant to enquire whether a given mixed solvent like urea + water mixtures will resist the centrosymmetric ordering of the ion more, or less than pure water.

In this communication, we report the viscosities of the solutions of KCl and NaCl in aqueous urea solutions at higher concentrations at 30 and 35°. We have tried to utilise some of the numerous empirical relations that have been put forward for aqueous electrolyte solutions².

Einstein³, treating the liquid as a viscous continuum with rigid spherical particles, deduced eqn. (1) by classical hydrodynamic methods, where ϕ denotes

$$\eta_r = 1 + 2.5 \phi \quad \dots (1)$$

the volume fraction of the solute electrolyte and η_r is the relative viscosity. The relation (2) of Jones and Dole⁴ equation

$$\eta_r = 1 + A \sqrt{C} + BC \quad \dots (2)$$

(where A and B are the inter-ionic forces in the viscosity and solute-solvent interaction coefficients¹ and C is the concentration of the solute electrolyte in m.l.⁻¹) is only applicable to dilute solutions ($C \leq 0.1 M$). However, at higher concentrations ($C \geq 0.1 M$), B swamps out the effect of A, resulting in equation (3).

$$\eta_r = 1 + BC \quad \dots (3)$$

For higher concentration of electrolyte Moulik⁵, Thomas⁶ and Vand⁷ have put forward the equations (4), (5) and (6), respectively

$$\eta_r = M + K'C^2 \quad \dots (4)$$

$$\eta_r = 1 + 2.5 \phi + 10.05 \phi^2 \quad \dots (5)$$

$$\ln \eta_r = \frac{2.5 \phi}{1 - Q \phi} \quad \dots (6)$$

In these equations Q is an interaction parameter dealing with mutual interference between the spheres and their Brownian motion, ϕ is a volume fraction given by $C\bar{V}$ where $\bar{V}$ is the effective rigid molar volume, and M and K' are constants. A comparative study of these equations over a wide range of concentration for a number of salts is reported by Moulik⁵.

Experimental

The salts, KCl and NaCl, were of AnalaR grade. Urea (G.R.) was used as such.

Densities of the solutions were measured using pycnometers (50 ml) with double capillary, which were calibrated with distilled water. Viscosities were determined by calibrated Ostwald viscometers of U-tube type as per British Standard specifications. All measurements were carried out at constant temperature within $\pm 0.01^\circ$. The flow time was recorded by a calibrated stop watch. The time of flow for each reading did not exceed by 0.2 sec and hence the error was ± 0.04 to $\pm 0.08\%$. Density readings did not differ by $0.0002 \text{ g. mol}^{-1}$ and hence are accurate upto 4 in 10^4 . The weight percent of urea was 5, 10, 15 and 20.

Results and Discussion

The η_r and ρ/ρ_0 values of the electrolytic urea solutions (Table 1) follow the same pattern as the pure electrolytic solutions and equation (3) has been used to obtain viscosity B-coefficients and Thomas

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TABLE 1—RELATIVE VISCOSITY (η_r) AND DENSITY (ρ/ρ_0)

Conc. mol. l ⁻¹	KCl				NaCl			
	η_r		ρ/ρ_0		η_r		ρ/ρ_0	
	30°	35°	30°	35°	30°	35°	30°	35°
	5% Urea							
2.0	1.3845	1.4282	1.4437	1.4282	1.5697	1.5854	1.2852	1.3988
1.5	1.2814	1.3270	1.3266	1.3270	1.4166	1.4251	1.2897	1.2932
1.0	1.1928	1.2232	1.2220	1.2232	1.2694	1.2763	1.1946	1.1977
0.75	1.1484	1.1697	1.1691	1.1697	1.2000	1.2091	1.1475	1.1538
0.5	1.1142	1.1132	1.1153	1.1132	1.1322	1.1354	1.1002	1.1022
0.4	1.0853	1.0905	1.0909	1.0905	1.1061	1.1062	1.0802	1.0814
0.3	1.0655	1.0681	1.0678	1.0681	1.0780	1.0775	1.0604	1.0606
0.2	1.0465	1.0456	1.0468	1.0456	1.0527	1.0531	1.0405	1.0416
0.1	1.0154	1.0222	1.0134	1.0222	1.0250	1.0253	1.0205	1.0225
	10% Urea							
2.0	1.3546	1.3607	1.3983	1.4018	1.5735	1.5817	1.3545	1.3579
1.5	1.2675	1.2737	1.3023	1.3098	1.5107	1.4295	1.2684	1.2762
1.0	1.1812	1.1861	1.2076	1.2096	1.2739	1.2768	1.1829	1.1847
0.75	1.1389	1.1426	1.1577	1.1589	1.2034	1.2040	1.1412	1.1425
0.5	1.0964	1.0998	1.1069	1.1088	1.1363	1.1351	1.0953	1.0967
0.4	1.0781	1.0813	1.0854	1.0870	1.1088	1.1070	1.0765	1.0777
0.3	1.0601	1.0589	1.0647	1.0611	1.0827	1.0801	1.0583	1.0596
0.2	1.0370	1.0460	1.0437	1.0463	1.0558	1.0526	1.0400	1.0409
0.1	1.0223	1.0226	1.0214	1.0216	1.0297	1.0261	1.0214	1.0223
	15% Urea							
2.0	1.3390	1.3239	1.3816	1.3737	1.5412	1.6895	1.2970	1.2951
1.5	1.2561	1.2565	1.2867	1.2994	1.4262	1.3921	1.2525	1.2551
1.0	1.1725	1.1718	1.1927	1.1944	1.2752	1.2697	1.1694	1.1710
0.75	1.1324	1.1316	1.1471	1.1434	1.2053	1.2001	1.1282	1.1294
0.5	1.0910	1.0888	1.0997	1.0999	1.1353	1.1311	1.0864	1.0870
0.4	1.0695	1.0717	1.0780	1.0807	1.1074	1.1046	1.0696	1.0702
0.3	1.0549	1.0537	1.0601	1.0507	1.0799	1.0779	1.0529	1.0535
0.2	1.0369	1.0366	1.0403	1.0406	1.0537	1.0517	1.0358	1.0361
0.1	1.0186	1.0127	1.0205	1.0147	1.0276	1.0260	1.0186	1.0186
	20% Urea							
2.0	1.3195	1.3226	1.3553	1.3586	1.6187	1.5955	1.3143	1.3175
1.5	1.2432	1.2700	1.2681	1.2978	1.4296	1.4363	1.2358	1.2382
1.0	1.1663	1.1678	1.1813	1.1835	1.2806	1.2783	1.1591	1.1607
0.75	1.1287	1.1292	1.1393	1.1403	1.2104	1.2075	1.1224	1.1237
0.5	1.0877	1.0884	1.0950	1.0969	1.1422	1.1372	1.0839	1.0848
0.4	1.0717	1.0719	1.0770	1.0776	1.1142	1.1101	1.0678	1.0685
0.3	1.0542	1.0543	1.0580	1.0584	1.0861	1.0757	1.0511	1.0516
0.2	1.0356	1.0371	1.0389	1.0396	1.0563	1.0514	1.0345	1.0350
0.1	1.0197	1.0192	1.0206	1.0204	1.0284	1.0242	1.0178	1.0180

and Vand equations with some modifications and Moulik equation as such to get different parameters of the equations employing both graphical and least square methods. The B values of the electrolytes are given in Table 2 and the values of the different parameters of the equations, employing both graphical and least square methods are given in Table 3.

$$\frac{\eta_r - 1}{C} = 2.5\bar{V} + K_s \bar{V}^2 C \quad (\text{Thomas}) \quad \dots (7)$$

$$\frac{1}{C} = 1.085 \bar{V} \frac{1}{\log \eta_r} + K \bar{V} \quad (\text{Vand}) \quad (8)$$

where K and K_s respectively have been used instead of Q in Vand equation and 10.05 in Thomas equation.

Equations (7) and (8) fit well with the viscosity data in aqueous solution. The activation parameter calculated by Goldsack and Franchetto⁶ could not be done as the measurements have been done only at 30 and 35° because of hydrolysis at 37°.

TABLE-2

B

l.mol⁻¹

Wt. % of Urea	KCl		NaCl	
	30°	35°	30°	35°
0	0.2000	0.2174	0.3125	0.3000
5	0.1925	0.1904	0.2950	0.2900
10	0.1750	0.1666	0.2650	0.2950
15	0.1650	0.1640	0.2800	0.2750
20	0.1550	0.1523	0.2650	0.2550

The equation of Moulik in its original form (upto 0.5 M) and those of Thomas and Vand in slightly modified form hold good within certain concentration ranges. It is evident from the results in Table 3 that the viscosity data in the ternary system can not be explained by a single equation. The values of $\bar{V}$ for KCl and NaCl obtained from

TABLE-3
 Moulik equation

Wt. % of Urea	KCl				NaCl							
	M	30°	K'	M	35°	K'	M	30°	K'	M	35°	K
0	1.21		0.375	1.21		0.412	1.20		0.273	1.18		0.271
5	1.17		0.2125	1.24		0.170	1.21		0.274	1.19		0.262
10	1.19		0.181	1.20		0.160	1.22		0.265	1.17		0.263
15	1.18		0.174	1.18		0.164	1.27		0.273	1.14		0.253
20	1.18		0.175	1.18		0.166	1.24		0.274	1.16		0.221

Thomas equation										
	V	Ks	V	Ks	V	Ks	V	Ks	V	Ks
0	0.086	0.3545	0.074	0.5945	0.103	1.24	0.100	0.298		
5	0.094	0.396	0.083	2.89	0.104	1.26	0.102	0.396		
10	0.100	5.12	0.081	3.45	0.107	-1.06	0.105	0.398		
15	0.103	5.2	0.099	3.22	0.108	1.14	0.106	0.476		
20	0.110	2.4	0.104	2.22	0.110	1.34	0.112	0.572		

Vand equation										
	V	Ks	V	Ks	V	Ks	V	Ks	V	Ks
0	0.080	-2.5	0.078	-2.76	0.109	-1.26	0.102	-2.26		
5	0.096	-2.65	0.092	-1.77	0.106	-1.36	0.098	-1.98		
10	0.120	-9.07	0.083	-3.93	0.105	-4.3	0.099	-1.97		
15	0.124	-4.4	0.094	-0.99	0.108	-3.2	0.100	-2.20		
20	0.126	-3.2	0.099	-0.98	0.112	-4.0	0.102	-1.80		

both Thomas and Vand methods are in good agreement and these values increase with the increase in urea concentration. This may be ascribed to the increase in the electrostatic attraction between water dipole and the ion.

Breslau and Miller⁹ have suggested a relationship between $\bar{V}$ and B for uniunivalent electrolytes (eq. 9).

$$B = 2.90\bar{V} - 0.019 \quad \dots (9)$$

The equation (9) has been tried but it does not hold good, but a linear relation of the type

$$B = a'\bar{V} + b' \quad \dots (10)$$

where a' and b' are constant, holds good. The ratio of $B/\bar{V}$ for KCl is 2.5 at 0% urea and 1.2 at 20% urea whereas for NaCl it ranges from 3.0 to 2.4. This indicates that K^+ is a structure breaker but Na^+ is a structure maker i.e. promotes the solvent structure around ion.

Addition of small amounts of urea to water may give rise to two effects. If the urea is accommodated

in the solvent structure, it may strengthen the water structure and B value will increase with increase in urea content. Since urea is basic and water automatically acts as an acid, the three dimensional water structure is broken down and the B coefficient is expected to decrease with increase in urea content. The latter is in conformity with the experimental results.

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